

Present and Future of Composite Materials
for Automotive Application in Japan

Mitsuru Noguchi
Honda R&D Co., Ltd.

ABSTRACT

Material researches for automotive applications conducted in the late 80's attempted to take a full advantage of the superiority of Fiber Reinforced Plastics (FRP) as an industrial effort to meet the market demands for better fuel efficiency and design diversification. On the other hand, however, the problem of recycling the used vehicle components became a social issue during the same period. This concern delayed the development of composite materials using plastics as their matrices. As a result, the use of such composite materials even today might be considered as still premature.

This paper describes the recent specific examples of Fiber Reinforced Plastics and Metal Matrices Composite being applied to the automobiles manufactured in Japan and discusses the technological value in such applications. The paper also describes the future expectation for the composite materials for the automobile application based on the industry trend and market demand with an increased usage of composite materials.